

New mineralogical and geochemical data on a potential critical raw materials occurrence at Polski Gradets (Southeastern Bulgaria)

Milen Stavrev, Stoyan Georgiev, Irena Peytcheva, Elitsa Stefanova, Silvia Chavdarova

Geological Institute, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Acad. G. Bonchev Str., bl. 24, 1113 Sofia;
E-mail: mstavrev@geology.bas.bg

Нови минералого-геохимични данни за проявление на критични суровини край Полски Градец (Югоизточна България)

Милен Ставрев, Стоян Георгиев, Ирена Пейчева, Елица Стефанова, Силвия Чавдарова

Abstract. New mineralogical and geochemical data on wolframite, garnets, and scheelite (\pm molybdenite) in hydrothermal quartz veins and skarns from the area of the Polski Gradets ore occurrence (SE Bulgaria) are present. Wolframite is the main ore mineral partly replaced by irregular scheelite aggregates. It is mostly ferberite in composition and contains 57.47 to 72.63 mol% FeO, 22.11 to 39.01 mol% MnO and MgO from 3.52 to 6.29 mol%. The trace element concentration in the wolframites is dominated by Mo, Nb, and Cu. The studied garnets are grossular-andradites (Grs: 47.51 to 86.87 mol%; Adr: 0.00 to 52.49 mol%) enriched in V, Cr, and As.

Keywords: Polski Gradets ore occurrence, wolframite, scheelite, critical raw materials (CRM), geochemistry.

Introduction and geological background

The continuous development and improvement of new technologies globally implies an increasing consumption of metals like copper, gold, lead, silver, etc., but also a growing number of further raw materials, defined currently as “critical” and “strategic”. The metals are used as new “green” energy resources, in the metallurgy, chemical industry, communication, aviation, and other economic branches or numerous high-tech products. Here, we present some new data on tungsten-bearing mineralization at the Polski Gradets ore occurrence located south of the village with the same name. Tungsten (W) is one of the 34 raw materials included in the list of critical and strategic raw materials (CSRMs) of the European Commission (Grohol, Veeh, 2023).

In the area of Polski Gradets is cropping out a metamorphic basement affected by Early- to Late

Alpine deformations and faulting (Kozhoukharov et al., 1994; Ivanov, 2017; Fig. 1a). The high-grade metamorphic rocks (gneisses, schists, metaconglomerates) are described as Proterozoic to Paleozoic in age, while the low-grade metamorphics (mica schists, metasandstones, and diverse marbles) are referred to as the Ustrem Formation of Triassic age. These basement rocks host the complex Late Cretaceous Polski Gradets granitoid pluton, consisting of quartzdiorites, diorites, granodiorites, leucogranites (Kamenov, Tarassova, 1995). Scarce intermediate to acid dykes cross-cut the granitoids (Nedjalkov, 1983). Based on its geochemistry the Polski Gradets pluton granitoids are defined as I-type and resulting from fractionation of magma that is sourced in the subcontinental mantle lithosphere and assimilation of crustal rocks. The age of the magmatic rocks was initially between 72 and 68 Ma by K-Ar isotope method (Kamenov, Tarassova, 1995) but later the

precise ID-TIMS U-Pb zircon data point to 78.27 ± 0.18 Ma emplacement (Georgiev et al., 2012). The link of the W-mineralization with the pluton was confirmed by U-Pb dating of wolframite at 79.0 ± 6.8 Ma (Peytcheva et al., this volume). Paleogene to Neogene sediments (clays, sands, coal, limestones) and Quaternary alluvial to proluvial deposits form the youngest cover in the study area.

In a metallogenic aspect, the Polski Gradets ore occurrence is designated as an individual manifestation within the Strandzha Ore Region during the intra-collisional rifting stage of the Aline Metallogenic Epoch on the territory of Bulgaria (Popov, Popov, 2022). Data for W-bearing ore mineralization and associated hydrothermal alterations are included in three unpublished reports (between 1966 and 2004, Bulgarian Geofund) and some papers (Nedjalkov, 1983; Tarassov, Iliev, 1992; Kamenov, Tarassova, 1995, Tarassova et al., 1996). The W-bearing ore zones are generally N-S trending as various alteration (silicification, greisen-like, and phyllic) is omnipresent. The most common ore minerals are wolframite, scheelite, molybdenite, and pyrite. They usually form single crystals to aggregates mainly in bigger veins and/or veinlets into the central parts of the Polski Gradets pluton. Chalcopyrite, bismuthinite, hematite, pyrrhotite, powellite, and bornite are rare.

A distinct sulfide mineralization is observed along the eastern contact of the Polski Gradets pluton with the host metamorphic rocks. The mineral association within the hydrothermal veins includes pyrite, molybdenite, chalcopyrite, galena, sphalerite, bismuthinite, cosalite, scheelite, bornite and less common native gold, hematite and magnetite (Tarassova et al., 1996). In the northwestern periphery of the pluton, diverse scheelite-bearing (\pm chalcopyrite and hematite) garnet-pyroxene-epidote exoskarns are formed. Epidote-pyroxene skarn bodies are established north towards the village of Polski Gradets containing mainly pyrite mineralization. Three stages of hydrothermal mineral deposition are distinguished: quartz-wolframite, quartz-scheelite, and quartz-sulfide. Two stages of the ore-forming process are distinguished (Tarassova et al., 1996) as follows: (i) earlier quartz-wolframite stage including wolframite-molybdenite-scheelite and magnetite-ilmenite-hematite associations, and (ii) later quartz-sulfide stage represented by sulfide mineralization.

Sampling and methods

Five wolframite-bearing quartz vein specimens and 3 skarn samples were collected for the present study. Most of the area south of the village of Polski Gradets and around the studied ore occurrence is currently cultivated land and the exposure of the rocks

is minimal. However, field relationships between the different lithologies were observed, and the skarn samples were taken from a relatively large outcrop.

The mineral associations were studied using a polarizing microscope Leica DM750P at the Geological Institute, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (GI-BAS), and by a JEOL JXA-8530F Scanning electron microscope with Wavelength-Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM-WDS) at the Earth Science Institute of the Slovak Academy of Sciences (SAS), Banska Bystrica, respectively. Sixty analyses were performed on ore and silicate minerals. Trace element measurements by LA-ICP-MS (PerkinElmer ELAN DRC-e ICP-MS attached to a New Wave UP193FX LA system) and high-resolution Cathodoluminescence (CL) images of W-bearing mineralization by Cathodyne Optical Cathodoluminescence (Newtec Scientific, France) were performed at GI-BAS.

Results and discussion

The exoskarn mineralization from the area of the Polski Gradets ore occurrence appears as a relatively thick (up to 10–12 m) aureole between the granitoids of the Polski Gradets pluton and host metamorphic units. Their mineral association is dominated by garnet (up to a few cm), which give the skarns a striped appearance (Fig. 1b, c). Diopside is the other main skarn mineral but in a subordinate quantity. Epidote, calcite, quartz, \pm titanite, \pm rutile, \pm scheelite, \pm zircon are less common. Garnets are usually medium to coarse-grained, highly fractured, and light brown in colour. SEM-BSE (back-scattered electron) images show that some of the garnet grains are inhomogeneous (shade zones of Fig. 1d). The darker parts are marked by depletion of Fe and weak enrichment in Al, Ca, and Si compared to the lighter sectors of the same grains. Other minerals of the skarns form small crystals and aggregates and/or fill cracks. SEM images also show some contrast in the pyroxene aggregates. Their predominantly darker appearance is due to the relative enrichment of Mg and corresponding depletion of Fe, while the lighter zones are typically enriched in Fe and Al. The studied garnets are mainly grossulars to grossular-andradites (based on 18 analyses – Grs: 47.51 to 86.87 mol%; Adr: 0.00 to 52.49 mol%; Prp, Alm, Sps: 0.00 to 29.61 mol%; Fig. 1e). The general crystal-chemical formula of the grains is $(\text{Ca}_{1.95-3.00}\text{Mn}_{0.00-0.07}\text{Fe}^{2+}_{0.00-0.78}\text{Mg}_{0.00-0.01})_{2.64-3.01}(\text{Al}_{0.92-2.31}\text{Fe}^{3+}_{0.00-1.07}\text{Ti}_{0.00-0.04})_{1.99-2.36}(\text{Si}_{2.91-3.00}\text{Al}_{0.00-0.09})_{3.00}\text{O}_{12}$. The measured by 10 analyses trace elements have relatively low content: V (22–140 ppm), Cr (3–63 ppm), and As (3–63 ppm). Rare earth element (REE) concentrations vary between 6 and 46 ppm. Despite the slight differences in some of the analyses,

Fig. 1. (a) simplified geological map of part of south-eastern Bulgaria (modified after Kozhoukharov et al., 1994) with the location of the Polski Gradets ore occurrence; the inserted map on the top left is after Ivanov (2017); (b, c) field views of the garnet-bearing skarns; (d) SEM-BSE image in part of large garnet from the studied skarns; (e) ternary diagram of the analyzed garnet compositions; (f) UCC normalized REE patterns of the garnets; (g, h) field view of some wolframite-bearing quartz vein samples; (i, j, k, l) SEM-BSE images of some ore-bearing samples; (m) UCC normalized REE patterns of the wolframites; (n) CL image of large prismatic wolframite crystal (on the right; non-fluorescent) replaced by scheelite with typical bright bluish-white fluorescence. Abbreviations: Grt, garnet; Cal, calcite; Qz, quartz; Wlf, wolframite; Sch, scheelite; Mol, molybdenite.

the chondrite-normalized REE distribution displays patterns with predominantly stronger middle rare earth elements (MREE) and heavy rare earth elements (HREE) enrichment along with light rare earth elements (LREE) depletion (Fig. 1f). One of the analyses has a relatively distinctive REE pattern characterized by enrichment of the LREE to the MREE and slightly HREE depletion. The distribution of the last pattern reflects the composition of the darker zones in the garnets. Bigger REE variations have Ce (0.1–4), Nd (0.6–24), Sm (0.5–6.2), Gd (0.4–5.4).

Wolframite forms usually single long prismatic black crystals and/or clusters of multiple smaller grains in nests and aggregates (Fig. 1g, h). In most samples, it fills voids among the main quartz mass of veins associated with fine crystalline quartz. Strongly oxidized pyrite and chalcopyrite are the other established ore minerals. The studied wolframite has a composition close to ferberite end-member of the hübnerite-ferberite series. The mineral contains 74.53 to 77.23 wt% WO₃, 14.25 to 17.95 wt% FeO and 5.18 to 9.55 wt% MnO (based on 114 analyzed points). Except for MgO (0.49 to 0.88 wt.%), the rest of the analyzed oxides reveal insignificant concentrations. The crystal-chemical formula of the wolframites is (Fe_{0.60–0.75}Mn_{0.22–0.40}Mg_{0.04–0.07})_{1.01–1.06}W_{0.98–1.00}O₄. In the BSE images (Fig. 1i, j, k, l), areas of different contrast are observed, which is due to very slight variations in the contents of the main components. The established by 24 analyses trace element concentrations in the studied crystals were dominated by Mo (63–955 ppm), Nb (12–334 ppm), Cu (up to 1055 ppm), Sc (17–239 ppm), Ti (17–103 ppm), Zn (20–43 ppm), and V (6–32 ppm). Similarly to garnets, wolframites are characterized by low REE values. Their upper continental crust (UCC) normalized patterns show an obvious stepwise trend towards enrichment from LREE to HREE (Fig. 1m). Most of the distributions have slight negative Ce anomalies, as well as minor Eu anomalies.

Microscopic, SEM-BSE and CL images (Fig. 1n) show that scheelite mineralization is formed by replacement of an earlier wolframite. Scheelite is deposited mainly along the wolframite peripheries as irregular aggregates, or forms vein-like aggregates around cracks, giving a netlike view to the earlier wolframite. On the same images, some inhomogeneity in the composition of the scheelite grains is also evident, while the SEM-WDS results show relatively “clean” compositions represented by W (79.55–80.97 wt%) and Ca (19.58–20.49 wt%). The darker areas are characterized by slightly lower W contents compared to the lighter zones. The mineral diversity in the studied ore samples is complemented by lamellar molybdenite flakes enriched in Re (0.1–0.5 wt.%) and W (0.8 wt.%). Some possibly even later and/or secondary molybdenum- and

tungsten-bearing mineral phases have also been identified. Their compositions (51.13–71.09 wt% MoO₃; 24.24–25.94 wt% CaO; 5.92–71.09 wt% WO₃) are relatively close to those of powellite and Mo-scheelite (67.68–70.84 wt% WO₃; 20.22–20.84 wt% CaO; 5.71–6.23 wt% MoO₃).

Conclusions

This study provides new data on the trace element content in garnets and wolframite, supplementing data on the composition of these minerals. Distinctive feature of the ores is the replacement of wolframite by scheelite. A possible decrease in fluid pressure with constant Ca/Fe (Ca/Mn) in the vein-type mineralization hosted by granitoids is suggested, as their Ca content is much less compared with the marbles in the area (Liu et al., 2021). Insignificant REEs in the wolframite crystals compared to other W-bearing deposits (Deng et al., 2019) and a trend of enrichment of HREE compared to LREE are characteristic. Future research of the mineral association of Polski Gradets will provide a more complete characterization of the CRM mineralization and the processes of ore deposition.

Acknowledgements: The study was supported by the AGEMERA project, which has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101058178. The authors thank Sergiy Kurylo for performing the SEM-WDS analyses at SAS.

References

- Deng, X.-D., T. Luo, J.-W. Li, Z.-C. Hu. 2019. Direct dating of hydrothermal tungsten mineralization using in situ wolframite U–Pb chronology by laser ablation ICP-MS. – *Chem. Geol.*, 515, 94–104; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemgeo.2019.04.005>.
- Georgiev, S., A. von Quadt, C. A. Heinrich, I. Peytcheva, P. Marchev. 2012. Time evolution of a rifted continental arc: Integrated ID-TIMS and LA-ICPMS study of magmatic zircons from the Eastern Srednogorie, Bulgaria. – *Lithos*, 154, 53–67; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lithos.2012.06.020>.
- Grohol, M., C. Veeh, 2023. *European Commission: Study on the Critical Raw Materials for the EU – Final Report*. Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs, Publications Office of the European Union; data.europa.eu/doi/10.2873/725585.
- Ivanov, Zh. 2017. *Tectonics of Bulgaria*. Sofia, St. Kliment Ohridski Univ. Press, 332 p. (in Bulgarian with English abstract).
- Kamenov, B., E. Tarassova. 1995. The Polskigradets pluton from Eastern Bulgaria – petrology, geochemistry and ore mineralizations. – In: *Proceeding of the XV Congr., CBGA, Athens, Geol. Soc. Greece, Spec. Publ.*, 4, 2, 527–532.
- Kozhoukharov, D., S. Savov, G. Chatalov, E. Kozhoukharova, I. Boyanov, E. Chelchiev. 1994a. *Geological Map of Bulgaria on Scale 1:100 000 with Explanatory Note. Topolovgrad Map Sheet*. Geology and Mineral Resource Committee, Enterprise of Geophysical Survey and Geological Mapping, 73 p.
- Liu, X., C. Xiao, Y. Wang. 2021. The relative solubilities of wolframite and scheelite in hydrothermal fluids: Insights from thermodynamic modeling. – *Chem. Geol.*, 584, 120488; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemgeo.2021.120488>.
- Nedjalkov, N. 1983. The wolframite mineralization at Polski Gradec, Sliven District. – *Rev. Bulg. Geol. Soc.*, 44, 3, 304–307 (in Bulgarian with English abstract).
- Popov, P., K. Popov. 2022. *Metallogeny of Bulgaria (with a Metallogenic Map of Bulgaria on Scale 1:500 000)*. Sofia, First Edition, BMGK Comers Ltd., 426 p. (in Bulgarian with extended abstract in English).
- Tarassov, M., R. Iliev. 1992. Wolframite from an occurrence at the village of Polski Gradets. – *Rev. Bulg. Geol. Soc.*, 53, 1, 11–16 (in Russian with English abstract).
- Tarassova, E., M. Tarassov, Yu. Christova. 1996. Hydrothermal metasomatites related to the Polski Gradets pluton, Eastern Srednogorie. – *Rev. Bulg. Geol. Soc.*, 57, 2, 69–74 (in Bulgarian with English abstract).